

Best Practice Document

Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples

Part 1: General Instructions

Annex 2.1 to AD4.1

WP 4 – T4.1

Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Planning the Collection of Human Samples	4
3. Precautions in the pre-analytical phase	5
4. Sampling	6
4.1. Precautions and basic containment when handling human samples	6
4.2. Preparations for Sampling	6
4.2.1. Vessels and tubes for sampling and storage	6
4.2.2. Pre-treatment of vessels, tubes and cryovials for sampling and storage	7
4.2.3. Labelling	8
4.3. Samples for Human Biomonitoring	10
4.3.1. Urine	11
4.3.2. Blood	11
4.3.3. Hair	12
4.3.4. Further matrices	12
4.3.5. Field blanks	12
5. Sample conservation, storage & shipment	14
5.1. Sample conservation and storage	14
5.2. Transport of samples	14

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Acronyms

CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
DINCH	Diisononyl 1,2-cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid
h	hour
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
ID	Identifier
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
min	minute
ml	milliliter
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PP	Polypropylene

1. Introduction

Human biomonitoring (HBM) is a powerful tool in the field of public health, although the lack of harmonization among the different HBM studies/programs can considerably limit the comparison of results and their global interpretation and subsequent translation into policy actions. Thus, in order to make an efficient use of the results of HBM studies possible it is necessary to build a harmonized framework covering all stages of the HBM studies.

The Best Practice document series is based on the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) on Obtaining Human Samples developed in the framework of the Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) and updated in PARC. It is intended to be used for a harmonized and standardized collection of human samples to obtain HBM data, that are comparable between individual studies of the different EU countries/regions. It provides an overview of the general procedure for the collection of human samples to be used in PARC and is currently divided into the following parts:

Part 1	Best Practice for the Sampling of Human Samples Part 1: General Instructions including preparations for sampling sample collection, processing and storage
Part 2	Best Practice for the Sampling of Human Samples Part 2: Collecting Urine Samples
Part 3	Best Practice for the Sampling of Human Samples Part 3: Collecting Blood Samples
Part 4	Best Practice for the Sampling of Human Samples Part 4: Collecting Hair Samples

Note: It is important to emphasise that depending on the target biomarker, additional treatments or precautions may be required. In addition, the definition of the minimum amount of sample taken depends on the amount needed for the subsequent chemical analysis, which in turn depends on the analytical method, limit of quantification, etc. This is particularly important for biomarkers that have not yet been defined but will be analysed in PARC in the future. Therefore, these questions must be discussed and determined in advance with the laboratory responsible for the analysis.

Any deviation from this best practice should be documented in detail.

2. Planning the Collection of Human Samples

Preparatory to each sampling, all aspects of sample collection and processing to storage and distribution should be defined in detail in study, sample collection, processing and storage protocols.

Pertaining to the PARC general surveys the study owner on the national survey should provide detailed instructions on how, where, which, and when human samples are to be collected and processed. These instructions should include specifications of needed materials, required volume for each matrix, labelling, etc. The procedure for collecting the sample types described below refers only to the already confirmed target biomarker addressed so far in PARC and samples required for the respective analysis. For the collection of urine & blood samples to be used in PARC, part 2 & 3 of this SOP can be used as a basis.

Detailed information on the PARC General Survey including the timeframe, sample size, target groups, pre-defined criteria, biological matrices, etc. is given in the document [PARC General Survey Design](#) (WP4, Task 4.1, Activity 4.1.1, Subactivity, 4.1.1.2 PARC Aligned Studies).

3. Precautions in the pre-analytical phase

The pre-analytical phase comprises all actions and aspects that occur prior to the analytical phase and should be considered as part of the laboratory works. This phase involves all preparation steps, sample collection, handling, aliquoting and storage, transport and conservation until the analysis.

Quality Control measures are commonly applied during the analytical phase by means of blanks, calibration curves, control samples, etc. in order to guarantee the reliability of their results. Control measures are often absent from the pre-analytical phase, however, all the precautions and controls measures taken during chemical analysis are useless if the samples have already been contaminated or altered during the previous steps such as sampling, transport or processing. Indeed, the pre-analytic phase has been identified as more error-prone than other intra and post-analytical steps [1, 2].

Control of the pre-analytical phase is even more important in HBM studies involving the general, supposedly non-exposed population than in other kinds of studies involving biological samples. On one hand, the type of samples analysed is important because when measuring an environmental chemical there is a risk of sample contamination due to the ubiquitous presence in the environment. On the other hand, the exposure to environmental chemicals usually occurs at low concentrations and their levels in biological matrices tend to be low, thus meaning that the influence of a potential contamination on the results is high.

As such, it is essential to identify and avoid, or at least minimise, the possible sources of contamination. In this regard, two main groups of factors should be considered:

Influencing factors

These factors are specific for each biomarker and are present before the sampling. The biological half-life of a chemical, alcohol consumption, medication intake or individual habits such as diet, are examples of influencing factors that can modify the internal levels of the chemical of interest. Therefore, the factors influencing the target biomarker must be identified and considered in the sampling strategy and finally during results interpretation.

Interfering factors

These factors may modify the concentration of the biomarker after sampling due to different processes such as external contamination, physical or chemical changes of the biomarker during transport or storage, or changes in the biological matrix (e.g., coagulation or sedimentation). In this case, it is essential to identify and avoid possible sources of contamination, such as exogenous contamination at the sampling location, contamination from the sampling equipment or vessels, or alterations due to absorption of the components to be analysed onto the walls of the vessel used.

General recommendations for the collection of human samples can be found in CDC (2018) [3].

Best practice:

Although different tools can be employed to control the pre-analytical phase SOPs are a valuable tool to increase the quality of the pre-analytical work. In general, a SOP is a clear, concise, comprehensive, and detailed step-by-step written description of a sampling or recruitment procedure, analytical method, etc. Specifically pertaining to the pre-analytical phase, additional quality control measures e.g., the use of **field blanks** during fieldwork, the collection of replicate samples, the **pre-cleaning of the sampling material** or the **control of the background contamination in sampling material** are highly recommended and should be part of the respective SOP.

The sampling SOP should also describe the measures for an unambiguous identification of the specimens and related documents (questionnaires, personal data, etc.) and processes for a standardized conservation and storage of the samples.

Finally, a written record of every event that occurs during sampling and all sample-related parameters (date and time of collection, volume, length, colour, etc.) will help in the identification of potential problems, for example, cross-contamination of a sample (e.g., urine sample contaminated with blood from menstruation). Additionally, a well-documented sampling procedure facilitates communication and avoids misunderstandings and errors within the fieldworkers' team and between fieldworkers and laboratory staff.

4. Sampling

4.1. Precautions and basic containment when handling human samples

According to the WHO laboratory biosafety manual, in situations when the information is insufficient to perform an appropriate risk assessment, for example, with clinical specimens or epidemiological samples collected in the field, it is prudent to take a cautious approach to specimen manipulation [4].

- Standard precautions should always be followed, and barrier protections applied (gloves, gowns, eye protection), whenever samples are obtained from patients ([Laboratory biosafety manual, 4th edition: Personal protective equipment \(who.int\)](#)).
- Basic containment – Biosafety Level 2 practices and procedures should be the minimum requirement for handling specimens.
- Biological materials should be processed by well-trained and qualified staff
- Transport of specimens should follow national and/or international rules and regulations (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-7-2-strategy-and-sops-for-human-sample-exchange-including-ethical-demands/>).

Note: Potential risks and instructions for safe handling of biological materials should be summarized in an operating instruction.

4.2. Preparations for Sampling

Note: Detailed documentation of all used material (e.g., devices, reagents, tubes) is strongly recommended and includes at a minimum, the manufacturer, model numbers, lot numbers, and expiration dates.

4.2.1. Vessels and tubes for sampling and storage

Best practice:

To guarantee comparable samples, **best practice** would be to purchase collection vessels, tubes and cryovials from the same brand and the same batch. Since this approach is only hardly realizable for different HBM surveys conducted in different European counties within PARC, we recommend at least to aliquot samples into **sterile cryovials made of medical grade polypropylene, free of leachable, heavy metals, and DNase/RNase suitable for the used storage technology**. This will minimize potential contaminations and increase the comparability of the sample quality. The designation "sterile" is not sufficient for the intended use. Avoid coloured plastics and cryovials containing o-rings, because of the increased risk of contamination from colouring agents or o-ring materials. Additionally, ensure that only cryovials from the same manufacturer and preferably with the same lot number are used for the samples in a coherent study.

4.2.2. Pre-treatment of vessels, tubes and cryovials for sampling and storage

Best practice:

To minimize manufacturing-related background contamination, **standardised cleaning** of all vessels and cryovials should be performed. Standardized cleaning with **methanol, nitric acid, and ultra-pure water** is commonly applied to minimize contaminations resulting in more standardized sampling material.

Urine collection vessels as well as all cryovials should be rinsed as described below.

Material needed for the pre-treatment

- Sampling vessels
- Cryovials
- Variable pipettes with corresponding pipette tips
- Laboratory balances
- Laminar-flow safety cabinet (class 2)
Fume cupboard with solvent cabinet
- Acid and alkali cabinet
- Ultra-pure water ($> 18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$)
- Methanol CH_3OH 99.8% p.a.
- Nitric acid HNO_3 65% p.a., ISO diluted
- Stands for sample cryovials

Pre-treatment of urine collection vessels

Urine vessels should be washed with 10% nitric acid in purified water solution in order to eliminate background contamination. The detailed procedure is described below:

1. Prepare a 10% nitric acid solution from nitric acid 65% extra pure and purified water.
2. Put the solution in a tank.
3. Open the vessels and put vessels and lids into the tank. Ensure that all of them are completely immersed.
4. Vessels should be immersed in this tank at least for 3 h (preferably overnight).
5. Take out the vessels from the acid tank and put them in a first tank with purified water. Shake for 2-3 min. Then, change the vessels and lids to a second tank of purified water. Shake for 2-3 min.
6. Take out vessels and lids and put them face down in a clean filter paper in order to dry them or leave vessels upside down in a safety cabinet (class 2) to dry.
7. Once the drying is finished, lids are screwed to the resulting nitric acid pre-treated vessels. It is useful to make a mark indicating the minimum amount of urine required. Then, put the pre-treated vessel into a zip-lock plastic bag (or similar) in order to be sent to the survey office.

The acid solution can be reused until one month after its preparation. All the procedure must be done in a chemical fume hood with the suitable personal protective equipment.

Pre-treatment of cryovials

1. Prepare all necessary materials and the 10% nitric acid solution
2. Open the cryovials
3. Rinse all cryovials including the caps with
 - a. **methanol** to remove organic contaminations: cryovials should be half-filled with methanol, closed & shaken for a minute, then dispose the methanol

- b. with the **10% nitric acid solution** to remove inorganic contaminations: cryovials should be completely filled with 10% nitric acid solution, closed & shaken for a minute, afterwards leave the solution in the cryovials overnight (min. 12 h), then dispose the acid solution
 - c. 3 times with **ultra-pure water** as final stage of cleaning cryovials should be completely filled with ultrapure water, closed & shaken for a minute, then dispose the ultra-pure water
4. Leave the cryovials in respective cryovials racks upside down in a safety cabinet (class 2) to dry
 5. Close the cryovials in the safety cabinet

Note: If pre-treatment of the sampling vessels and cryovials cannot be carried out for any reason, please document this and describe the alternative QA/QC measure applied! As an example of an alternative QA/QC 5% of all urine vessels (after the cleaning procedure) can be randomly selected, filled with 200 ml purified water, shaken for 10 min, and aliquots analysed for the considered biomarkers.

4.2.3. Labelling

A standardized approach for labelling is required to assign unique identification codes for all samples collected to avoid any incorrect or double coding. However, the introduction of **standardised labelling** of the samples to be used for the general survey in PARC is a challenge, as in some European countries samples are collected as part of already established national surveys. We provide the following labeling strategy as a best practice recommendation for the harmonization of the labeling strategy with the occupational and health studies in PARC only. The final labeling strategy has to be aligned with the PARC data management plan.

Best practice:

For a sound sample tracking all used material must be precisely labeled throughout the single sampling and handling stages. Pre-labeling of collection vessels, tubes and cryovials is recommended. The label should be electronically readable, hence, the use of labels with barcodes (e.g., Code 128) that additionally include the human readable identifier is highly recommended to enable accurate sample tracking.

Materials that should be labeled include the following but are not limited to:

- urine sampling vessels,
- blood collection tubes,
- cryovials,
- freezer boxes.

Respective sheets with ID labels to use for labeling should be prepared and provided for immediate use.

Labels for the cryovials should contain as a minimum the following information and should be placed in a way such they are well readable with electronic barcode readers:

- **General survey (G)**
- **Country-ID (XX)**
(2-digit abbreviation code according ISO 3166, [Country Codes List - ISO ALPHA-2, ISO ALPHA-3 and Numerical Country Codes - Nations Online Project](#))
- **Target Group-ID (X)** (1-digit abbreviation as described below)

Target Group	Code
Children 6 - 11 years	C
Teenagers 12 - 17 years	T
Adults 18 - 39 years	A

- **Biological Matrix-ID (XX)** (2-digit abbreviation as described below)

Matrix	Sample type	Code
Urine	(First) Morning Urine	UM
	Spot (Random) Urine	US
Blood	Whole Blood	BW
	Plasma	BP
	Serum	BS
	DBS	BD
	VAMS	BV
Hair	Depending on hair length	HA

- **Participant-ID (XXX)**
three-digit running number of participants in each country (e.g., 001 for the first participant recruited, 002 the second and so forth).
- **Sample/Aliquot-ID (XXX)**

Example:

The following scenario is provided to illustrate the application of this convention: A participant aged 28 is recruited in France. He is the first participant recruited in that country and is providing his morning urine sample, which will be processed and aliquoted into 10 cryovials. The sample identification codes assigned for the 10 aliquots are therefore:

G-FR-A-UM-001-001

G-FR-A-UM-001-002

....

G-FR-A-UM-001-010

Note: Final labelling strategy has to be in line with the PARC Data Management Plan.

Material needed for the labelling

- Labels suitable for temperatures down to -80 °C or -196 °C depending on the used freezing technology
- Label printer and barcode scanner

Labelling of vessels, tubes and cryovials

Best practice:

Use chemically inert labels that withstand conventional freezing and liquid nitrogen storage without peeling or cracking.

Place the specific participant ID labels on all sampling materials so that when they are upright, the barcode looks like a ladder. This simplifies the use of electronic barcode readers.

4.3. Samples for Human Biomonitoring

The required biological matrices depend on the target biomarker and the age group. According to the PARC General Survey Design ([PARC General Survey Design](#)), the following matrices are expected* to be collected from the studies:

Table 1 – Samples types to be collected

Target Group	Biological Material	Sample type to be collected
Children 6 - 11 years	Urine	first morning urine
	Blood (only optional)	whole blood and serum (plasma)
	Hair	depending on hair length (see part 4)
Teenagers 12 - 17 years	Urine	first morning urine
	Blood	whole blood and serum (plasma)
Adults 18 - 39 years	Urine	first morning urine
	Blood	whole blood and serum (plasma)

If the expected matrices cannot be collected by a study this should be evaluated before inclusion of the study under the GS.

Table 2 - Overview of prioritized substance groups per age group for PARC Year 1 General Survey

	Children 6 – 11 years	Teenagers 12 – 17 years	Adults 18 – 39 years
Arsenic and its organic compounds	Urine		
Bisphenols	Urine	Urine	Urine
Mercury	Hair		
Metals (multi-elements)	Urine	Urine	Urine and Blood
Pesticides - Glyphosate/AMPA			Urine
Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Urine	Urine	Urine
Pesticides – Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)	Urine		Urine
Pesticides – Organophosphates (Chlorpyrifos)	Urine	Urine	Urine
PFAS	Serum	Serum	Serum
Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	Urine	Urine	Urine
Cotinine Creatinine Specific gravity	Urine	Urine	Urine

4.3.1. Urine

This biological matrix is the result of a filtration process that occurs in the kidneys to eliminate water-soluble toxins and waste from the body. Together with blood, urine is the biological matrix of choice in HBM studies as it is a non-invasive matrix, easy to collect and available in larger amounts than other matrices.

The most common urine samples are spot, first morning, and 24-h urine samples with each having its pros and cons depending on the addressed research question. Aiming at harmonizing sampling on a European level, within PARC 24-h urine samples are considered too cumbersome and impractical. To minimize the contamination risk and effort and so to increase the acceptance of participants, **morning urine samples** should be collected. However, when using morning (or spot urine) samples, the variability in the volume of urine produced needs to be corrected since the concentration of endogenous and exogenous chemicals can vary significantly from void to void depending on the hydration status, time of last urination, etc. This adjustment can be done by different methods, e.g., normalization of urinary biomarkers to urinary creatinine or specific gravity of the sample [5-7]. However, it is valuable to record multiple urinary parameters, since their suitability for standardization may vary related to the target biomarker and the type of urine sample taken.

Best practice:

To guarantee the comparability of analytical results **first morning urine (entire bladder emptying)** should be collected and only if not possible, the collection of spot urine samples should be considered.

Note: Quality-assured analysis of creatinine and specific gravity as a measure for urinary dilution were defined as obligatory for all urine samples.

Critical remark: A spot urine sample reflects only a specific point in time and does not provide information on the exposure of an entire day. If spot urine samples are collected, the concentration of the target biomarker may be below the LOQ due to sample dilution or could be overestimated due to the short time between ingestion and excretion.

Detailed instructions on the collection of urine samples are given in Part 2 of the Best Practice Document Series.

4.3.2. Blood

Blood is an ideal matrix for most chemicals because it is in contact with all tissues and is in equilibrium with the organs and tissues where chemicals are deposited. The collection of blood samples requires trained sanitary staff, special precautions related to the handling of biological material.

Different types of blood samples can be collected. Depending on the substance and its distribution between blood plasma and the cellular components of the whole blood, a decision must be made about which matrix is more suitable for the planned analysis. Samples of whole blood require additives to prevent coagulation. Plasma and serum are derived from whole blood having undergone different biochemical processes after blood collection.

Best practice:

In studies where multiple aliquots are required for different analyses, a **sample collection protocol** should specify the exact procedure including the volume needed and the order in which the aliquots should be collected. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses.

Detailed instructions on the collection of blood samples are given in Part 3 of Best Practice Document Series.

4.3.3. Hair

Human hair is a non-invasive matrix that is easy to collect following a simple process that requires only minimal training and no special materials for sampling.

Mercury analysis through hair samples is a non-invasive method to assess mercury exposure and so ideal for children. Hair is easy to collect, transport and store following a simple process that requires only minimal training and no special materials for sampling. Hair samples can provide insight into both the short- and the long-term exposure. In addition, hair analysis is considered to be an optimal biomarker for assessing mercury exposure, and total mercury content (THg) in hair is an accepted biomarker for chronic dietary methylmercury (MeHg) exposure.

Detailed instructions on the collection of blood samples are given in Part 4 of Best Practice Document Series.

4.3.4. Further matrices

Currently, it is being discussed whether further samples types (e.g., DBS, VAMS) will be integrated in the PARC concept for the aligned studies. Depending on the outcome of these discussions, corresponding SOP parts will be developed and made available.

4.3.5. Field blanks

To control analytical abnormalities with respect to the target biomarkers and since future analysis of samples collected in PARC may address chemicals that are not focused on now, it is recommended to **include field blanks** in the complete pre-analytical process as a real world-control of any potential background contamination. Contamination can occur at all stages of the whole pre-analytical workflow – from collecting, processing to transporting and storage. Field blanks in this regard are samples made of ultra-pure water, which undergo the entire pre-analytical process and are treated, processed and analysed in the same way as the collected human samples. Field blank samples can be used to identify background contamination from the sample material, handling and/or transportation and hence should be routinely included in each survey as part of the pre-analytical QA/QC measures.

Best practice:

Since field blanks should cover all pre-analytical steps and since different sample types are collected and processed differently and, in addition, samples are pre-treated differently with respect to the analysis of the exposure biomarker of interest, it is best practice to provide field blanks for each of the sample types collected and each target biomarker. For PARC, this includes but is not limited to urine, whole blood and serum (plasma) samples. Prepare an additional 10% of the total number of study participants as blank samples per sample type.

Note: If it is not realizable to generate field blank samples of 10% of the total sample size, at least generate one field blank samples per PSU and sample type. As a result, a minimum quantity of field blank samples of 2% of the total sample size and per sample type is required.

Preparation of field blanks

Urine field blanks:

- Fill pre-treated (cleaned) urine sampling vessel half of the volume with ultra-pure water (18.2 MΩcm) in a laminar flow safety cabinet/work bench
- Provide the prepared field blank vessel in addition to the urine sampling vessel to 10% (min 2%, see note above) of the study participants and ask the respective participant to open and close the field blank vessel in the bathroom parallel to collecting the urine sample. Field blank vessel should be open for the time of the urine collection
- Note date and time of filling and label as defined for the collected human sample

Whole blood field blanks:

- Fill blood collection tube (2K EDTA) with ultra-pure water (18.2 MΩcm) at the sampling site according to the sampling protocol. Make sure that you use the same puncture set (butterfly needle set, phlebotomy needle) that is used in the study
- Note date and time of filling and label field blank the same way as is defined for the collected human samples

Serum field blanks:

- Fill blood collection tube (without clotting agent) with ultra-pure water (18.2 MΩcm) at the sampling site according to the sampling protocol. Make sure that you use the same puncture set (butterfly needle set, phlebotomy needle) that is used in the study
- Note date and time of filling and label as defined for the collected human samples

Plasma field blanks:

- Fill blood collection tube (2K EDTA) with ultra-pure water (18.2 MΩcm) at the sampling site according to the sampling protocol. Make sure that you use the same puncture set (butterfly needle set, phlebotomy needle) that is used in the study
- Note date and time of filling and label as defined for the collected human samples

Handing of field blank samples

Note: The number of field blank aliquots per sample type depends on the number of biomarkers to be analysed in that sample type. For example, if it is planned to analyse ten different biomarkers in first morning urine samples, at least 10 urine field blank aliquots need to be prepared from all the field blank samples (10 % of the total number of participants of the study) as a control for each of the ten analysis. The exception is for biomarker sets that can be analysed in one aliquot of one sample type, e.g., a multi-element analysis in plasma would require only one blank aliquot, as several elements are analysed in a single plasma aliquot. However, as more analyses than those planned so far may be added, significantly more aliquots of the field blank samples should be generated and stored frozen with the remaining collected human samples.

- Label sampling vessel according to the defined labelling strategy for the respective samples type (barcode, ID) as if it would be a real sample
- Register IDs of the field blanks as such in your database
- Deliver field blank sample to lab for sample preparation randomized with collected human samples
- Process field blank samples the same way human samples are processed according to the defined processing protocol for the respective samples type (Part 2 or Part 3 of this document)
- Store sample aliquots the same way as the human samples according to the defined freezing and storage procedure
- Deliver filed blank aliquots randomized with human sample aliquots to the analytical laboratory for the analysis of the considered biomarker

5. Sample conservation, storage & shipment

As already indicated at the beginning of the chapter on sampling (page 3), according to the WHO manual on laboratory biosafety manual it is prudent to take a cautious approach to specimen manipulation.

5.1. Sample conservation and storage

In the context of medical research, it has been proven that different storage temperatures and temperature fluctuations during storage influence sample integrity with regard to biomarkers of interest [8-11]. The impact of storage conditions has also been demonstrated in cases of individual HBM relevant substances, e.g., polychlorinated biphenyls, brominated flame retardants, some pesticides or arsenic species [12, 13], it is therefore reasonable to assume that other environmental pollutants might be equally affected by different storage conditions. Only the availability of high-quality and comparable samples will guarantee reliable and comparable analytical results. Hence, harmonization and standardization of sampling and related biobanking processes on a European level are a prerequisite. To avoid as much sample alteration induced by storage conditions temperatures below the glass transition temperature [14] are required.

Best practice:

Due to the relatively high investment needed to install liquid nitrogen (LIN)-based storage technologies needed to achieve temperatures below the glass transitions temperature, not every partner within PARC might be able to realize storage conditions to protect samples from alteration as far as possible. Since comparability of the samples has to be guaranteed, though, it has been agreed in the PARC consortium to harmonize **storage conditions between PARC partners for short- and long-term storage to at least -80 °C or lower.**

To avoid sample alterations caused by resting times at room temperature, samples should be processed and frozen within 24 hours. If possible, store samples within this 24 at about 4-8 °C.

Hair samples do not need special storage conditions; they can be stored at room temperature but must be kept away from moisture, for example in a drawer or a box.

5.2. Transport of samples

For detailed instructions on sample exchange please see HBM4EU deliverable report *D.7.2 "Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands"*.

Appendix

Parameters included in the PARC QA/QC

SUBSTANCE GROUP	BIOMARKER	MATRIX
Phthalates	MEP	Urine
	MBzP	
	MiBP	
	MnBP	
	MCHP	
	MnPeP	
	MEHP	
	5OH-MEHP	
	5oxo-MEHP	
	5cx-MEPP	
	MnOP	
	OH-MiNP	
	cx-MiNP	
	OH-MiDP	
	cx-MiDP	
DINCH	OH-MINCH	Urine
	cx-MINCH	
Bisphenols	BPA	Urine
	BPF	
	BPS	
PFAS	PFPeA	Serum
	PFHxA	
	PFHpA	
	PFOA	
	PFNA	
	PFDA	
	PFUnDA	
	PFDoDA	
	PFBS	
	PFHxS	
	PFHpS	
PFOS (sum of all isomers)		
Pesticides		Urine
Metals		Urine
		Blood
		Hair

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